

POLITICAL SCIENCES

ESTABLISHING PEACE! WHY U.S. COUNTERINSURGENCY EFFORTS FAILED IN AFGHANISTAN?

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Abstract

The current paper analyzes the failure of the United States (U.S.) counterinsurgency efforts in Afghanistan using a qualitative approach. Senior bureaucrats, ambassadors, political figures and Afghan locals were interviewed to identify why U.S. counterinsurgency efforts failed in Afghanistan. The study argues that stigmatized locals, imbalance of power, poor governance and lack of local autonomy in governance for defeating the Taliban's insurgency undermined the United States' counterinsurgency efforts in Afghanistan. The paper suggests that the United States could have had a more profound engagement with the local Afghans and could have provided the local rural institution with more autonomy for solving the Afghan problem. Further, the U.S. could have looked for an effective mediator to establish sustainable regional peace. The lesson learnt may be helpful for world leaders and policymakers in their efforts to win the war against terror.

Keywords: Counterinsurgency, Stigmatization, Local Autonomy, Taliban, the United States and Afghanistan.

1. Introduction

Global terrorism threatens world peace (Djumala et al., 2022). The USA entered Afghanistan to wage war against terror. However, twenty years afterwards, it left Afghanistan to the mercy of the Taliban. Many people view this as a failure of the USA to create a strong Government that could keep fighting the terror outfits and sustain a democracy (Rashid, 2008; Tariq et al., 2020; Kolenda, 2021). The paper examines the USA's failure in its counterinsurgency effort in Afghanistan. The lesson learnt may be helpful for world leaders and policymakers in their efforts to win the war against terror.

With the aid of NATO and more than 40 nations, the USA invaded Afghanistan in 2001 as part of the war on terror to bring about harmony in the area. The United States has been calling its military campaigns "Operation Enduring Freedom" (2001–2014) and "Operation Freedom's Sentinel" (2015–present) to justify them. However, over 100,000 citizens and over 60,000 security personnel have died due to these armed efforts to promote peace (U.N. News, 2020; Al Jazeera, 2019). According to the extant literature, these fatalities resulted from U.S. peacekeeping efforts. Despite all their efforts and setbacks, the U.S. peacekeeping mission in Afghanistan was a resounding failure.

Further, the U.S. was involved in multiple wars, whether with Iraq, China or Pakistan. However, the purpose of the article is not to contrast U.S. involvement in Afghanistan with other interventions, like the conflict in Iraq. Both are examples of extensive conflict following 9/11. (Jacobson, 2010). As the Iraq conflict ended, violence in Afghanistan worsened, and fatalities skyrocketed (Jacobson, 2010: 587). The U.S.'s longest-running war—in Afghanistan—deserves careful consideration. It is crucial to comprehend the U.S.'s successes and failures in the larger framework of efforts to legitimize a foreign intervention in Afghanistan for the state's and the region's future security. The significance of this article has increased with recent shifts in the character of U.S. involvement in Afghanistan and the military withdrawal setting the Taliban to the throne.

Methodologically, this article provides a qualitative analysis of this intervention and why it failed by conducting interviews with senior bureaucrats, ambassadors, political figures and Afghan locals. After this introduction, a brief consideration of the respondents interviewed was provided and is followed by an analysis of the factors that led to the failure of U.S. counterinsurgency efforts in Afghanistan in light of existing peacebuilding literature. The concluding analyses search for viable post-conflict solutions and guide world leaders.

2. Respondents Profile

Table 1 provides the list of the respondents interviewed for analyzing the factors leading to the failure of U.S. counterinsurgency efforts in Afghanistan. A total of sixty interviews were conducted, including educators, bureaucrats, ambassadors, political figures, journalists and Afghan locals. However, only thirty-

four respondents provided their demographics, and others chose to keep them anonymous. The average interview time was between 1 to 1.5 hours, and the respondents were interviewed in a semi-structured manner. Some of the questions were closed-ended, and some were kept open-ended.

Table 1.

Respondent's Profile					
Respondent (s)	Age	Gender	Education	Occupation	Ethnicity
R-1	65	Male	PhD	Educator	Persian
R-2	49	Male	Masters	President (Society)	Pashtun
R-3	40	Male	Masters	Ambassador	Pashtun
R-4	65	Male	PhD	Retired E.U. Official	European
R-5	57	Male	Masters	Peace activist	Pashtun
R-6	44	Female	P.hD	Former diplomat	Pashtun
R-7	44	Male	P.hD	Water Resource Management, Consultant	Afghan/Australian
R-8	59	Male	P.hD	Academic	Afghan
R-9	29	Male	P.hD	Researcher	Pashtun
R-10	40	Female	Masters	Former diplomat	Pashtun
R-11	38	Female	Bachelors	Academic	N/A
R-12	48	Male	Masters	N/A	Pashtun
R-13	52	Male	Masters	Humanitarian and peace activist	Pashtun
R-14	47	Male	P.Hd	Media/ Academia	Afghan
R-15	32	Male	Masters	Business Advisor	Pahtoon
R-16	61	Male	Masters	Former diplomat & CEO	Pashtun
R-17	75	Female	Bachelors	Former diplomat & Consultant	American
R-18	67	Male	P.hD	Medical doctor	Afghan
R-19	65	Male	Masters	Minister in the Government	Afghan
R-20	32	Male	Masters	Business Advisor	Pashtun
R-21	67	Male	P.hD	Medical doctor	Afghan
R-22	38	Male	Masters	Research Analyst	American
R-23	35	Male	Masters	Director of a Civil Society	Afghan
R-24	60	Female	P.hD	N/A	Afghan
R-25	27	Male	Masters	Journalist	Pashtun
R-27	61	Male	Masters	Former Ambassador	Pashtun
R-28	37	Male	Masters	Senior Analyst	American
R-29	63	Male	Masters	Country director	Tajik
R-30	42	Male	Masters	Intra-Afghan Negotiation Member	N/A
R-31	34	Male	N/A	Journalist	Sadat
R-32	45	Male	Masters	Republican Member	Pashtun
R-33	57	Male	Bachelors	Chairman of a Peace Institute	Afghan
R-34	41	Female	Masters	Former MP	Mix

3. Factors leading to the failure of U.S. counterinsurgency efforts:

Improper Balance of Power in the Region

Galtung (1967) defined balance of power as a natural concept that would preserve autonomy and peace. Suppose one is in favor of large military establishments. In that case, peace thinking to the effect that peace can only be obtained utilizing a balance of power policies (with their well-known tendency towards built-in arms races) is usually considered good peace thinking (Bizhan, 2022). Alternatively, if one is in favour of weak military establishments, peace thinking of a more pacifist variety is usually welcome, regardless of its other properties (Vaynman et al., 2021). Only very few thinkers, we assume, would consider the balance of power an autotelic value, i.e. a goal in its own right; they would regard it as a condition of peace which in

turn would be seen as an autotelic value. However, not so with the element of "development": it is also seen as an autotelic value by many, i.e., a value worthy of being pursued in its own right, regardless of whether it leads to peace. In the current study, many respondents have a similar opinion. One of the respondents, when asked for his opinion on U.S. efforts in Afghanistan, provided that *"Their non-balance support across the country was a huge cost to everyone. They have spent hundreds of billions of \$ to support the warlords, not the ordinary Afghan"*. Another respondent said, *"In my opinion the U.S. peacebuilding efforts were imbalanced. The administration, particularly in the last stages, seemed fatigued, neglecting the suggestions of its army generals to keep at least 2500 to 3000 soldiers in the country until two sides set seriously on the table"*. Thus, the lack

of balance of power also failed the U.S. peacebuilding efforts in Afghanistan.

Stigmatization as a Deterrent to Peacebuilding

All the stakeholders should work on decreasing the stigma if peace has to be established (Unfried et al., 2022). The local people of Afghanistan had a strong stigma against the U.S. in their minds. Some think of them as war-builders rather than peace-builders, and some regard them as power-hunters. Such strong stigmas against the U.S. disrupted the peace process due to a lack of trust (Aroussi, 2021). The Afghan people felt discriminated against at the hands of the U.S. army. Our study also found the same. One of the respondents provided that *"USA fear republics, where people government in third world countries, like the Arab spring top-ple downed all USA allied dictators, therefore, USA got in an agreement with Taliban and made them a dictator government, as it benefits USA regional objectives in Central Asia"*. Moreover, stigmas compel an individual to hold strong opinions against the U.S. Another respondent provided that *"I think there was not peacebuilding process from the beginning, USA was trying to let Taliban government over Kabul, which indirectly benefits USA in the regional destabilization."*

Further added, *"The efforts by the United States could not be described as peacebuilding efforts; it was merely trying to reach a deal to have a face-saving arrangement and quit"*. Thus, the above excerpts provided evidence of heightened stigmatization. It could have been quickly taken care of, but the U.S. failed to acknowledge it. The inter-group contact theory states that one crucial channel to reduce such prejudices is through increased empathy and decreased anxiety. Therefore, increasing inter-group contact would have promoted positive attitudes and behaviours towards the U.S. efforts (Paolini et al., 2021). However, the failure to reduce the stigma led to the failure of peace.

The role of Hostility, International Capacity & Local capacity to change

Peacebuilding strategies must be designed to address particular conflicts, and broad parameters that fit most conflicts can be identified. Strategies should address the local roots of hostility, the local capacities for change, and the (net) specific degree of international commitment available to assist sustainable peace (Doyle & Sambanis, 2000). The literature also suggests that the dimensions substitute for one another; that is, more of one substitute for less of another; less extreme hostilities substitute for weak local capacity or minor international commitment (Mazarr et al., 2019). Our study also found strong support for the same that led to the failure of U.S. peacebuilding efforts:

a) Hostility

When peace has been made or enforced, peacebuilding is an effort to address the root causes of the conflict and strengthen regional conflict resolution capabilities. (Pukallus, 2021). A deeper civil society, more vital state institutions, increased political involvement, land reform, and regard for ethnic identities are all seen as methods to increase the likelihood of peaceful administration (Alvarez et al., 2000). Our study, by analyzing the responses, found support for the same. One of the respondents provided that - *"The U.S. does*

not have strong support and good partnership to prevent insurgency in Afghanistan. They trust Pakistan in many areas. They do not have a focused plan to help Afghans for sustainable economic growth, justice, peace and other basic rights". Another respondent provided that -

"The invasion of Afghanistan by the USA was not associated with any peacebuilding efforts. Instead, their focus was tackling Al-Qaeda and defeating the then-Taliban regime. The U.S. from the very beginning had no effective strategy for peacebuilding, and most of their presence in Afghanistan remained uncoordinated and mismanaged". Thus, the hostility towards the peacebuilding efforts also led to the disruption in Afghanistan.

b) International capacity

According to Doyle and Sambanis (2000), to produce specific post-conflict results, the pre-and postwar levels of local capacities interact with current international capacities. The task is to determine the most influential foreign aid to maximize the room for peace currently available for given levels of local capability and hostility. Our study also found that the right level of international assistance was not provided. Some of the respondents opined that -

"When the talks began under the Trump administration, there was no effort to put solid, provable conditions on the Taliban. When Biden took over, he made no effort to hold the Taliban accountable for failing to meet the terms of intra-Afghan talks and a durable ceasefire."

Further, the fiscal and social capacities of war-torn nations differ. Some have a strong foundation for economic growth and social ability among an educated populace. (Hultman et al., 2019). Others start destitute and become even poorer as a result of the conflict. In both situations, reconstruction is essential. The greater the social and economic destruction, whether consent-based multidimensional policing or non-consent enforcement followed by and including multidimensional peacekeeping, the more significant the multidimensional international role must be (Doyle & Sambanis, 2000). One of the respondents provided that

"The main problem was the warlords who were not interested in bringing peace where they would lose power. The international community was also not on the same page regarding peacebuilding in Afghanistan. Moreover, the neighbouring countries were playing their cards in the process, thus opposing or even nullifying whatever was against their interest." It clearly indicated the lack of international capacity to resolve the conflict and the vested interest each stakeholder has in peace.

c) Local capacity to change

The only way to establish sustainable peace is to look for local roots of hostility and the local capacity to change (Doyle & Sambanis, 2000). Due to the low opportunity cost of conflict and the potential for private gains from violence, actors with low levels of economic growth and other deficiencies in local capabilities may resort to violence (Collier and Hoeffler 2004). Reconciliation is more challenging because the experience of conflict has increased hostility. One of the respondents

provided that the *"Peacebuilding process was the requirement of Afghan people, and it was an obligation to the USA, as they lost the war against Taliban."* Thus, the locals are already willing to change and want peace to be established.

Further, another respondent added, *"It is paradoxical that the U.S. neglected realities on the ground and the role of regional actors in Afghanistan and claimed that they want to establish peace"*. The above excerpts provided that the Afghan locals are in a capacity to restore peace in the region. However, the U.S. and the international agencies failed to capture that force and hence, failed in the peacebuilding process.

Local autonomy via socio-economic development & state legitimacy

In conjunction with local interactions, socio-economic growth has reinforced local autonomy by emphasizing alternative local governance systems. (Krampe, 2016). We still do not fully comprehend how local autonomy functions in ongoing peace processes characterized by a delicate interaction between the state and community (Leonardsson, 2023). In particular, knowledge is scarce about the local dynamics that had a role to play in peacebuilding. Our study found that peace can never be established without giving autonomy to the locals and ensuring their active participation. One of the respondents provided for the U.S. that *"They have spent hundreds of billions of \$ to support the warlords, not the ordinary Afghan"*, indicating an apparent lack of vision to support the localities.

Further, another respondent added that the *"Americans did not understand to whom how should they talk, regional countries, powers, internal Afghan affiliates, because they were not having an accurate understanding of these actors, and were not having a crucial decision from the beginning of their intervention in Afghanistan, so they lost their way to find a peaceful solution to Afghanistan conflict"*. Thus, the lack of local knowledge aggravated the situation, and thus, peacebuilding mandates the involvement of locals. Further, the respondents constantly opined that -

"U.S. peacebuilding efforts in Afghanistan were politicized and immensely compromised by other factors, including maintaining their interests in the regions regardless of how much the ordinary Afghans should pay." Moreover, one of the respondents claimed that the U.S. efforts were *"Not locally owned, ill-informed and non-inclusive"*. Thus, the U.S. efforts to establish peace in the region failed as they lacked local knowledge and did not give locals the autonomy to run the government. Moreover, our study found that the locals had no role in the peacebuilding process and, thus, failed substantially.

Control over geography

Natural resources and civil conflict have been the subject of a deluge of study since the late 1990s. Concerns about misspecification and spuriousness have also clouded quantitative studies of civil conflict and natural resources (Ross, 2004). Further, the extant literature provided that the correlation between the natural resource—civil war could be spurious: both civil war and resource dependence might be independently caused by some third unmeasured variable, such as the

weak rule of law (Vesco et al., 2020). Therefore, our qualitative study provided robust support for control over natural resources and wars. One of the respondents stated, *"They want to capture the Afghan region to gain control over it, to use it as a strategic resource to establish its control over the Middle East and not with an intent to support Afghans"*. The study found that, at times, not just the natural resources but the region itself acts as a resource. Hence, the U.S. entered to gain control over the region to have a strategic resource and, thus, failed substantially later.

Civil Resistance

Evidence suggests that nonviolent opposition is approximately twice as successful as military combat in the fight against dictators and the end of foreign occupations. The traditional scholarly emphasis on only violent methods has ignored the capacity of nonviolent movements to frequently better organize supporters, resist regime crackdowns, better develop innovative resistance techniques, and take on and defeat repressive regimes frequently to build stable democracies (Chenoweth et al., 2011). One of the respondents provided that they felt that

"The Afghan civil society had a minim role in the peace process mainly due to its lack of vision and in certain cases being sidelined by the key players/actors." Further, one of the respondents provided that *"There are thousands of organizations, groups as well as individuals across the country - rural and urban areas - in Afghanistan with views that are not necessarily in favour of any of the parties to the conflict"*. Thus, the civil society in Afghanistan had a minimum role to play; even those who were active had a difference in their opinion, and their interests clashed with the interests of other stakeholders (Cahill et al., 2019). Therefore, there is evidence that the peacebuilding process in Afghanistan faced resistance from civil society.

Lack of effective mediation

Conflict management techniques like mediation and peacebuilding are frequently employed. It is still debatable whether or not they are complementary and efficient means of putting a stop to violent disputes. (Clayton & Dorussen, 2022; Leeuwen et al., 2020). Peacekeeping strives to keep agreements from dissolving, whereas mediation seeks to enable mediated resolutions. However, peacebuilding and conciliation frequently co-occur (Greig & Diehl, 2005; Diehl & Regan, 2015). Various studies presented the substantial impact of mediation and peacekeeping on the frequency of conflict. Our study also supported the claim. One respondent stated, *"There is a need, but this time, any talk must be mediated by an Islamic organization or a strong Muslim country; without such mediation, peace is impossible in Afghanistan."* Thus, mandating the presence of an acceptable mediator. Further, it is provided by one of the respondents for the U.S. stated that *"They must have commentated to mediation, arbitration, and adjudication. No political will, warlords and the USA was looking after its regional interest rather than supporting Afghanistan"*. Thus, the evidence indicates a lack of an effective mediator in the U.S. peacebuilding process in Afghanistan. As a result, the efforts failed, and the Taliban took over the nation. The choice

of mediator would have probably resulted in more stability and effectiveness in governance. Sharma (2022) states that 69% of Afghans view India as Afghanistan's 'best friend country', followed by the USA (22%), Pakistan (10%), Russia (9%), Saudi Arabia (6%), and China (4%). In other words, mediation could have been sought from other perceived friendly nations. In particular, with strong Indo-US ties, greater involvement of India would have probably improved the previous government's effectiveness.

Others: Poor Governance led to disruption

The U.S. peacebuilding efforts in Afghanistan failed for several reasons, including lack of mediation, civil resistance or local autonomy (Stewart, 2021). The literature, as well as the interview excerpts, provided support for the same. However, other factors, such as poor governance, are pertinent to this situation (Evans & Kelikume, 2019). Our study also found the same wherein one respondent provided ".....no clarity on the purpose of their mission. Also, all actors and countries were not on the same page. Several competitions or wars were going on in Afghanistan. US-IRAN, US-China, US-Russia, US-Europe, Counter Narcotics, Counter Terrorism, bad governance and eventually building war economy which contributed to the failure of peacebuilding in Afghanistan." Also, some respondents provided that the U.S. lacks a long-term vision for the people of Afghanistan. One respondent stated, ".... Short-sighted vision with American interests as the main driver: leaving Afghanistan asap and having an Afghan government which could handle their counter-terrorism objectives."

Further, the lack of vision failed the U.S. to plan things. The study proved that ".... It was neither well planned nor executed. A decision was made in a hurry and implemented without making a proper arrangement." A recent study (Sharma, 2022) found that 78% of Afghans believe the erstwhile Afghanistan government misgoverned and mismanaged foreign aid. Further, the same study contended that 72% of Afghans believe that the Taliban takeover happened due to the corruption of local leaders.

The U.S. lacked planning and was short-sighted (Lebovic, 2019). This resulted in frequent changes in their strategy to tackle the region, creating chaos among the stakeholders. Thus, inviting other enemies to enter the region. Finally, the Afghans believed the U.S. was also unwilling to establish peace. One of the respondents provided that- "*The USA was not having any political will for peace in Afghanistan. It was trying to push the region into a regional conflict.*" Moreover, they also stated that

"The Afghan-centric notion of peace involves independence and sovereignty of the Afghan nation. The U.S. involvement was antithetical to the Afghan-centric notion of peace. Therefore, could never be any real U.S. effort towards peace as long as Afghanistan remained occupied. The genuine peace efforts would have been an unconditional withdrawal, but even after the withdrawal; the U.S. indirectly supported anti peace elements, imposed economic sanctions, and froze Afghan funds to keep Afghanistan in constant crisis. That re-

veals the ill intention of the U.S. part even after withdrawal". Thus, all these factors together led to the failure of U.S. peacebuilding efforts in Afghanistan.

4. Conclusion

The extant literature provided several factors for the failure of peacebuilding mechanisms. However, understanding the failure of the U.S. counterinsurgency efforts in Afghanistan was limited. Because of the dubious methods employed during military action, the War on Terror has obviously negatively impacted the West's moral standing. For their efforts to "permanently incapacitate Bin Laden and other al Qaeda leaders and their Taliban enablers," the USA has paid a heavy price (Jacobson, 2010: 586). The West's "appetite for military intervention" has, unsurprisingly, decreased due to the protracted military operations in Afghanistan and their inability to accomplish the intended goals (Barry, 2017: 137). The U.S. population is growing opposed to using military action in the future after learning about some of the crimes committed during the military intervention in Afghanistan (Newport, 2014).

Apart from all this, the study provided that the peacebuilding efforts failed as the U.S. could not manipulate the Stigmatized locals, the locals were not provided with autonomy, and their role was kept minimum in the peacebuilding process. Moreover, there was a lack of effective mediation, and the U.S. lacked a long-term vision for the people of Afghanistan. As a result, the U.S. has to withdraw itself from the region, placing the Taliban on the throne. The current study will guide future leaders, bureaucrats and other stakeholders in managing the peacekeeping processes and ensuring sustainable peace.

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